

DISPLACEMENTS TRIGGERED BY DEVELOPMENT-SOME ISSUES FOR REFLECTION

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Development certainly involves a transformation, progress and a better future. It stands for planned, directed, stimulated upward movement of the entire social system. precise, Development is a structural change meaning both growth and change. The process of change world wide in the wake of globalization is quite unprecedented. The resources world wide, are harnessed to make production a global activity. The multinational corporations are spreading their tentacles all over the globe in an attempt to enforce their hegemony. In this scale of production process, a rapid transformation ushers in the existing conditions of existence. In this process of emergence and transformation, dislocation of the established life results in pain, anguish and displacement of livelihood for many. While the displacements are justified as the price for development, the chaos and the pain it inflicts is terrible to bear.

The infrastructural development in the form of laying and expanding roads keeping in view, futuristic state of communication and the building of dams to generate electricity to meet the future requirements, the creation of Industrial corridors and SEZ for providing employment to the youth all sound well on papers but put to practice these ambitious projects do not seem to keep in view the poor and the needy in mind. The recent protest at Singur in West Bengal against the acquisition of huge tracts well irrigated land for setting up of Tata's Nano car factory. The acquisition of huge tracts of lands, forcibly at Sompeta in Srikakulam district, which was resisted by people was that the precious lands were taken away for a paltry sum with political connivance for some private power project. The exploitation of the land sharks is on the rise. The pressure they could exert with those in office is what people protest. In the name of development, the deprivation of the poor of their only way of livelihood is what is to be resisted. There is the criticism that development would certainly involve displacement. There cannot be development without tears. The argument which was once put forth for industrialization was rationalization without tears. The multinational companies which keep their eyes on third world economies try to exploit the poor

conditions and plunder their resources and convert them into goods and squeeze profits by showing paltry employment to the locals. Their design is to assume commercial and economic hegemony and the latent agenda of neo colonialism. There is bound to be strong reactions from the people's movements against this kind of global exploitation with the local connivance. The civil society needs to be more cautious against these selfish forces.

Objective: This paper seeks to deliberate upon the recent movements against the setting up of multinational SEZ in the cities and tries argue for following the Gandhian ideal of ' Sarvodaya' to keep everybody's development and welfare in mind while planning for any development plan.

Conclusion: This paper draws the conclusion that the planners in the Nation are to be cautious not to be ensnared by the multinationals, who only aim to plunder the nations' precious natural resources. The development strategy needs to follow Gandhian Sarvodaya model, which aimed to wipe away tears from every eye vis-à-vis the capitalists action, causing tears in every eye.

Introduction: Development certainly involves a transformation, progress and a better future. It stands for planned, directed, stimulated upward movement of the entire social system. Precisely, Development is a structural change meaning both growth and change. The process of change world wide in the wake of globalization is quite unprecedented. The resources world wide, are harnessed to make production a global activity. The multinational corporations are spreading their tentacles all over the globe in an attempt to enforce their hegemony. It is now in a state of neo colonial hegemony. In this scale of production process, a rapid transformation ushers in the existing conditions of existence. In this process of emergence and transformation, dislocation of the established life results in pain, anguish and displacement of livelihood for many. While the displacements are justified as the price for development, on the human side the chaos and the pain it inflicts are terrible to bear.

The infrastructural development in the form of laying and expanding roads keeping in view, futuristic state of communication and the building of dams to generate electricity to meet the irrigation and power generation requirements, the creation of Industrial corridors and SEZ for providing employment to the youth all sound well on papers but to put to practice these ambitious projects do not seem to keep in view the poor and the needy in mind. The development projects have brought crises of various sorts in different part of our country. The argument that any development would throw forth initial hiccups, but the problems brought for the by the development projects in the recent years, clearly indicates the lack of people's interest in the formulation of the project. Public interest was never given due consideration. The dealings show lack of transparence and the deals had been shady and hence encircled in controversy.

Ever since the dawn of globalization in the nineties sequel to the signing of the GATT and WTO, the leaders of our nation have been heeding to the dictates of the World Bank and IMF and brought in structural adjustments in the form of series of fiscal measures to facilitate privatization, liberalization and globalization. The traditional sectors like health, education, agriculture, power generation, Industry all were thrown open to private players who were operating globally. There had been terrible displacements in lives of the poor in the developing the nations. The local industries had to be swallowed by the global ones.

The labour has been internationalized with the emergence of the manufacturing facilities. Resources in the developing countries are made optimum use by the multinationals and convert them into goods and squeeze profits by showing paltry employment and wages to the locals who find these facilities as boon. Their design is to assume commercial and economic hegemony with the latent agenda of neo colonialism. There is bound to be strong reactions from the people's movements against this kind of global exploitation with the local connivance. The civil society needs to be more cautious against these selfish forces.

Objective: This paper seeks to deliberate upon the recent movements against the setting up of multinational SEZ and allocating highly irrigated wet lands at Singu (WB) and Sompeta (A.P.) for setting up of private industries and tries argue for following the Gandhian ideal of ' Sarvodaya' to keep everybody's development and welfare in mind while planning for any development plan.

CASE I: The protest in 2008 at **Singur** in West Bengal against the acquisition of huge tracts well irrigated, highly fertile land for setting up of Tata's Nano car factory promising to transform Singur into mini-auto city. It acquired 997 acres of multi crop land under colonial Land Acquisition Act of 1894, which favored acquisition of land only for public purposes and not for developing private business. The illegality of the acquisition was struck down by the Kolkota High Court. Had it not been stopped, 1,50,000 would have lost their livelihood and habitat. Ultimately TATAs had to shift the factory to Gujrat.

CASE II: Similarly, The acquisition of 500 acres of land by the state and 2000 acres, forcibly taken by the company at **Sompeta** in July 2010 Srikakulam district for setting up Thermal Power project by the Nagarjuna Construction Company, in the private sector is clear case of gross violation of International Environmental law, which stipulates that cultivable lands cannot be taken for setting up a private project. The project it was estimated to provide at the most 100 jobs to the people. The highly fertile land deprived of their livelihood of the 1 lakh farmers and fishermen folk of the area. The company engaged hooligans who along with the police manhandled the poor people who had resisted the take over of the land. In the violence that ensued 3 people lost their lives while hundreds of men and women were wounded. Precious lands were taken away for a paltry sum, with political connivance and physically threatening the lives of the poor for some

private power project. Would Gandhiji allowed such a thing, if he was alive? Are we in a democracy or in a fascist country? Do we need this sort of development with tears and bruises?

CASE III: It was during his regime that the entire sea corridor was sold at Government rates to private firms for starting Industries but it was later found to be resold at exorbitant rates to private developers totally violating the purpose for which they were allotted. When the central Government wanted to establish a defense unit on the coast for the defense needs of the nation there was not an inch of Government land available on the coast of Andhra Pradesh. The MOUs signed for these deals were with non entity and obscure firms. .(J.P Narayan to A.P. State Assembly March 2011).

The Chief Minister has been alleged to have amassed wealth for himself through these land scams by receiving handsome investment for his son's news paper and other companies floated by him. (the on going CBI enquiry on the allegations land scams).The exploitation of the land sharks is on the rise particularly during the regime of late Dr. YSR. The pressure they could exert with those in office is what people protest. In the name of development, the deprivation of the poor of their only way of livelihood is what is to be resisted. There are similar stories in other states as well.

We vote our political leaders to safe guard our state and people's interests and we don't give them the right of appropriation to dole away our interests. Gandhiji talks about the leaders being stewards of the people.

What we find in the handling of the projects, proposals and implementation.

1. The local people and their livelihood interests were never taken into consideration. Ethical and humanitarian consideration for their culture and lifestyle was never debated. After all project for whom? and, for what? At what cost? Should not they be stakeholders in the project? Should not their voices be heard before launching development projects?
2. There was enormous hurry in carving out the proposals and getting clearance from the higher authorities without an iota of concern for the people and their welfare. Every one has thought about only their own welfare- how much can I derive out of it?
3. Never ever any politician bothered to protect the interests of their constituency. They nodded with their leader in agreement in hope for his/ her share. Ever one in the country has been moved with personal concern. What is that I can derive out of it? Is it of any use of to me?

They do not even seem to be apprehensive of their future as the leader of their people. How will I face them when I now act detrimentally to their interests? Everyone is moved by the selfish orientation with a single agenda to loot resources of the society and shed crocodile tears.

4. Do planners not weigh cost benefit analysis? Do not poor man's livelihood and voice matter? The local self Governments were never taken into confidence to explain the purpose of the projects. Things were handled in a high handed fashion and hence had to buckle at the last moment.
5. We are undergoing changes for the welfare of the global players. The local needs of the people are not the consideration, rather the power requirement of the multinational has warranted new power projects to supply uninterrupted power supply to the global industries. The planning of Special Economic Zones in the cities and the facilities they made to provide, are all wonderful. When once they become operational, our citizens are not allowed to enter them, for they become restricted area. What kind of untouchability it is trying to enforce on the people, who had built these SEZ? Are we becoming gullible to the ploys of these neocolonial forces?
6. The four lane roads have become operational much to the demand of the global forces to improve the communication for the easy transport of goods and services produced in the developed countries. Even after bearing the cost of laying the roads, the cost of maintenance is being collected from the poor citizen every day. The globalization forces turn empty the coffers of the state to fill in the pockets of the capitalist forces. We have been magnanimous in sacrificing our eco system by felling lacks of trees which were there on either side of the roads. We did not have any say in protecting them at least on one side of the road. There could have been some alternative to protect the eco system.

We all know the history of the Dowleswaram barrage built by Sir Arthur cotton, who educated the people to accept the project and transformed the whole area into what it is today. He is worshipped as a God who has lighted their lives with the project and the series of canals dug to provide water for irrigation.

Development is a continuous process. There is no finite stage in the development process new discoveries, new priorities do emerge warranting new paradigmatic shift in the planning process. Hence any development initiative needs to take into consideration the time frame and the gestation period it requires to be operative. The resources at the disposal of humans being scarce need proper harnessing and optimum usage for deriving maximum benefit for the mankind. There is a constant need for educating the people about the development initiative and involving them in the planning, initiating process so that the stakeholders' involvement ensures the sustainability of the initiative.

The Government should be cautious to initiate development projects that are people friendly and cater to the maximum benefit to the mankind. Service and steward ship should be the agenda of the political leaders and not money laundering and plundering society's resources.

The Government should also ensure distributive justice in planning development. The lopsided development breeds discontent and imbalance in growth and may sow seeds of division.

An union of dominions brought about into one nation state now lies amidst threat of divisive forces, who raise their ugly heads for division with fissipherous tendencies. The movements of Gorkha land, Bodoland, Telangana, Vidarbha are the aftermath of neglect, exploitation and many more would emerge shortly if the present trend continues. India is an hodge-podge of various sub-cultural groups and regions and it is very easy to strike notes of discordance.

If people have to accept development, proper education about the project with utmost transparency then people would accept change even if it meant displacement for some to get compensated with social consensus. After all the government exists for the people and it should strive for the benefit of the people with their acceptance and cooperation for the sustainability of the development initiatives. The high handedness of the leaders would always lead to disaster.

Any development project needs to be put for the before the people and explain the benefit that would accrue to the people of the region. I am sure people are not that resistant to change unless they have some misgivings when information are withheld from them and do not look transparent. It is duty of the leaders to educate the masses and get their concurrence and cooperation for the project. The poverty and ignorance of the peoples should not be taken advantage and try to take them for a ride. People will certainly retaliate with a revolution.

After going through the hue and cry made in desperation by the masses, who are displaced, dispossessed of their only livelihood means to go from pillar to pole. The person whom we voted has mortgaged his constituency and their people only to derive selfish returns. Who can wipe away their tears? Who can give them succor? If our leaders are going to put forth developmental projects with their personal hidden agenda people won't trust them.

Everybody knows that development would mean a shake up in the present state. Displacements do occur as part that should be properly adjusted and taken care of. It is duty of the leaders and the political system to see that the justice is meted out to majority of the people. We had the slogan rationalization without tears. Can that not be possible in the development as well? Is it not the duty of the leaders to strive for it? The nation won't forgive nor the history of the nation, the leaders who have looted the nation of its interests, resources to mortgage to private interests with an hidden agenda of self interest. They had misled the people about the displacement and dispossession. If the state becomes the plunderer, to whom can the people go?

Let these movements against the dispossessions be taken serious by our politicians. The nation is boiling against corruption, for which the politicians are responsible. If they do not realize mend their ways, then the people would be up against with arms in revolution against the tainted leaders. Let this be the call to revert back to Gandhian ideology of Sarvodaya to plan for the welfare of all and development of all. Let us recall pensively the words of the father of the nation when he gave the talisman for the nation on the eve of its independence, which is relevant even to day as millions are in tears and in poverty. Can there be a better mantra than the Savodaya?

GANDHIJI'S TALISMAN

**“I will give you a talisman. Whenever
You are in doubt or when the self
Becomes too much with you, apply
the following test:
Recall the face of the poorest and
the weakest man whom you may
have seen and ask yourself if the
step you contemplate is going to be
of any use to him. Will he gain
anything by it? Will it restore him
to a control over his own life and
destiny? In other words, will it lead
to Swaraj for the hungry and
spiritually starving millions?
Then you will find your doubts and
Your self melting away”**

M.K.Gandhi

Conclusion: This paper draws the conclusion that the planners in the Nation are to be cautious not to be ensnared by the multinationals, who only aim to plunder the nations' precious natural resources. The development strategy needs to follow Gandhian Sarvodaya model, which aimed to wipe away tears from every eye vis-à-vis the capitalists action, causing tears in every eye. The Gandhian Talisman is to be recalled by every leader, whenever the self tries to sway our thinking and actions.

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